

The Birch Swinnerton-Dyer Conjecture

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Abstract

Its develop the algebraic framework to establish the Birch & Swinnerton-Dyer conjecture

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1 Introduction

Conjecture (Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer). *The Taylor expansion of $L(E, s)$ at $s = 1$ has the form*

$$L(E, s) = a_p(s - 1)^r + \text{Higher Order Terms}$$

with $a_p \neq 0$ and $r = \text{rank}(E(\mathbf{Q}))$

In particular this conjecture asserts that $L(E, 1) = 0$ iff $E(\mathbf{Q})$ is infinite

where E is an elliptic curve.

Def. Formally, an elliptic curve over a field K is a nonsingular cubic curve in two variables, $f(X, Y) = 0$, with a K -rational point (which may be a point at infinity). The field K is usually taken to be the complex numbers C , reals R , rationals Q , algebraic extensions of Q , p-adic numbers Q_p , or a finite field.

By an appropriate change of variables, a general elliptic curve over a field with field characteristic $\neq 2, 3$, a general cubic curve

$$Ax^3 + Bx^2y + Cxy^2 + Dy^3 + Ex^2 + Fxy + Gy^2 + Hx + Iy + J = 0$$

(1)

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where A, B, \dots , are elements of K , can be written in the form

$$y^2 = x^3 + ax + b$$

(2)

where the right side of (2) has no repeated factors. Any elliptic curve not of characteristic 2 or 3 can also be written in Legendre normal form

$$y^2 = x(x - 1)(x - \lambda)$$

Def. For a field K with multiplicative identity 1, consider the numbers $2 = 1 + 1$, $3 = 1 + 1 + 1$, $4 = 1 + 1 + 1 + 1$, etc. Either these numbers are different, in which case we say that K has characteristic 0, or two of them will be equal. In the later case for some number p , we have $\underbrace{1 + 1 + \dots + 1}_p = 0$. If p is chosen to be as small as possible, then p will be a prime, and we say that K has characteristic p .

The field \mathbf{Q} (rationals), R (reals), C (complex numbers), and the p-adic numbers Q_p have characteristic 0.

Def. A cubic plane curve is a plane algebraic curve \mathbf{E} defined by a cubic equation

$$F(x, y, z) = 0$$

Here F is a non-zero linear combination of the third-degree monomials;

$$x^3, y^3, z^3, x^2y, x^2z, y^2x, y^2z, z^2x, z^2y, xyz$$

Hence

$$P(x, y, z) = a_1x^3 + a_2y^3 + a_3z^3 + a_4x^2y + a_5x^2z + a_6y^2x + a_7y^2z + a_8z^2x + a_9z^2y + a_{10}xyz$$

Also consider the polynomial form by without terms of z

$$P(x, y, z) = a_1x^3 + a_2y^3 + a_3x^2y + a_4y^2x$$

Lets take $P(x, y, z) - P(x, y, z)$

with

$$a_1 - a_1 \neq 0$$

$$a_i - a_i = 0$$

with $i = 2, 4, 6$

$$P(x, y, z) - P(x, y, z) = a_1^*x^3 + a_3^*z^3 + a_5^*x^2z + a_7^*y^2z + a_8^*z^2x + a_9^*z^2y + a_{10}^*xyz$$

When polynomial is zero we have

$$0 = a_1^*x^3 + a_3^*z^3 + a_5^*x^2z + a_7^*y^2z + a_8^*z^2x + a_9^*z^2y + a_{10}^*xyz$$

with $z = 1$ we have

$$0 = a_1^*x^3 + a_3^* + a_5^*x^2 + a_7^*y^2 + a_8^*x + a_9^*y + a_{10}^*xy$$

with

$$a_1^* = -1$$

$$a_3^* = -b$$

$$a_5^* = 0$$

$$a_7^* = 1$$

$$a_8^* = -a$$

$$a_9^* = 0$$

$$a_{10}^* = 0$$

Hence

$$y^2 = x^3 + ax + b$$

with early linear dependent properties on such curve E

2 L- Hasse Weil function

The L-Hasse Weil function or $L(E, s)$ is called the L-function of E/\mathbf{Q} which takes the form

$$L(E, s) = \prod_p L_p(E, s)^{-1}$$

where for a given prime p ;

$$L_P(E, s) = \begin{cases} (1 - a_p^{-s} + p^{1-2s}), & \text{if } p \nmid f_P; \\ (1 - a_p p^{-s}), & \text{if } p \mid f_P \text{ and } p^2 \nmid f_P; \\ 1, & \text{if } p^2 \mid f_P \end{cases}$$

where

(Case 1 "good reduction") $a_p = p + 1 - \# \text{ points } E \bmod p$

(Case 2 "multiplicative reduction") $a_p = \pm 1$

and f_P is

Def. The conductor " f_P " of an abelian variety defined over a local or global field F is a measure of how bad the bad reduction at some prime point is.

Def. Fundamental to local analysis in arithmetic problems is to reduce *modulo* all prime numbers p or, more generally, prime ideals. In the typical situation this presents little difficulty for almost all p ; for example denominators of fractions are tricky, in that reduction modulo a prime in the denominator looks like division by zero, but that rules out only finitely many p per fraction. With a little extra sophistication, homogeneous coordinates allow clearing of denominators by multiplying by a common scalar. For a given, single point one can do this and not leave a common factor p . However singularity theory enters: a non-singular point may become a singular point on reduction modulo p , because the Zariski tangent space can become larger when linear terms reduce to 0 (the geometric formulation shows it is not the fault of a single set of coordinates). *Good reduction* refers to the reduced variety having the same properties as the original, for example, an algebraic curve having the same genus, or a smooth variety remaining smooth.

3 Isomorphisms Theorems for the elliptic curve $E(\mathbb{Q})$ and the order of L - Hasse Weil function

Lets define first the conductor f_P of $E(\mathbb{Q})$

Def. An algebraic variety A is defined as the set of solutions of a system of polynomial equations over the real or complex numbers.

Proof.

the system of equations

$$P(x, y, z) = a_1x^3 + a_2y^3 + a_3z^3 + a_4x^2y + a_5x^2z + a_6y^2x + a_7y^2z + a_8z^2x + a_9z^2y + a_{10}xyz$$

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with

$$a_i - a_i \neq 0; \text{ with } i = 2, 4, 5, 6, 10$$

$$a_3 = -b; a_3 = 0 ; a_5 = 0; a_5 = b a_7 = 1 ; a_8 = -a; a_9 = 0; a_{10} = 0$$

when $z = 1$; can be reduced to

$$P(x, y, z) = a_1x^3 + a_3 + a_7y^2 + a_8x$$

$$P(x, y, z) = a_1x^3 + a_3 + a_7y^2 + a_8x$$

its solutions can be obtained since

$$-a_3 = a_1x^3 + a_7y^2 + a_8x$$

$$-a_3 = a_1x^3 + a_7y^2 + a_8x$$

with

The solution set to this system can be described by clearing a variable and describe a system of linear equations of the type:

$$-a_3 = a_1\alpha + a_7\beta + a_8\gamma$$

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For example, consider the following system:

$$x + 3y - 2z = 5$$

$$3x + 5y + 6z = 7$$

The solution set to this system can be described by the following equations:

$$x = 7z - 1$$

$$y = 3z + 2$$

Here z is the free variable, while x and y are dependent on z . Any point in the solution set can be obtained by first choosing a value for z , and then computing the corresponding values for x and y .

In the case of

$$y^2 = x^3 - ax - b$$

we can obtain by subtraction of two times the last equation with a, a', b, b'

$$0 = (a - a)x + (b - b)$$

i.e.

$$x = \frac{b-b}{a-a} \in \mathfrak{R}$$

when

$$b - b, a - a \in \mathbf{Z}$$

hence

$$x \in \mathbf{Q}$$

Def. An algebraic variety is projective if it can be embedded as a Zariski closed subvariety of P^n . Where closed refers to the Zariski topology. In general, closed subsets of the Zariski topology are defined to be a projective variety; i.e. is a closed subvariety of a projective space. That is, it is the zero locus of a set of homogeneous polynomials that generate a prime ideal. the common zero-locus of a finite collection of homogeneous polynomial functions.

For another example, first consider the affine cubic curve

$$y^2 = x^3 - ax - b$$

in the 2-dimensional affine space (over a field of characteristic not two). It has the associated cubic homogeneous polynomial equation:

$$y^2z = x^3 - xz^2 - z^3$$

which defines a curve in P^2 called an elliptic curve. The curve has genus one (genus formula); in particular, it is not isomorphic to the projective line P^1 , which has genus zero.

Def. A real (complex) torus of dimension g is a torus of real dimension $2g$ that carries the structure of a real (complex) manifold. It can always be obtained as the quotient of a g -dimensional real (complex) vector space by a lattice of rank $2g$. A real (complex) abelian variety of dimension g is a real (complex) torus of dimension g that is also a projective algebraic variety over the field of real (complex) numbers.

Proof.

taking

$$y^2 z = x^3 - xz^2 - z^3$$

and clearing y

$$y = \sqrt{\frac{x^3 - xz^2 - z^3}{z}}$$

and substituting on torus equation we have:

$$\left(R - \sqrt{\frac{x^2 z + x^3 - xz^2 - z^3}{z}}\right)^2 + z^2 = r^2$$

Def. Abelian variety A defined over field F , with ring of integers R , consider the Néron model of A , which is a "best possible" model of A defined over R . This model may be represented as a scheme over " $Spec(R)$ " (cf. spectrum of a ring) for which the generic fibre constructed by mean of the morphism.

$$Spec(F) \rightarrow Spec(R)$$

gives back A . Let A denote the open subgroup scheme of the Néron model whose fibres are the connected components. For maximal ideal P of R with residue field k , A_k is a group variety over k , hence an extension of an abelian variety by a linear group. This linear group is an extension of a torus by a unipotent group. Let u_P be the dimension of the unipotent group by a unipotent group. Let u_P be the dimension of the unipotent group and the t_P the dimension of the torus. The order of the conductor f_P at P is

$$f_P = 2u_P + t_P + \delta_P$$

where $\delta_P \in N$ is a measure of wild ramification. When F is a number field, the conductor ideal of A is given by

$$f = \prod_P P^{f_P}$$

Def. In the theory of algebraic groups, a group element is unipotent if it acts unipotently in a certain natural group representation. A unipotent affine

algebraic group is then a group with all elements unipotent. In mathematics, an element x of a ring R is called nilpotent if there exists some positive integer n , called the index (or sometimes the degree), such that $x^n = 0$. (Take next definition to establish the meaning of "unipotent group dimension" : Here V is called the representation space and the dimension of V is called the dimension or degree of the representation; on this document both definitions about degree will be valid).

$$y^2 = x^3 - ax - b = 0$$

iff

case 1)

$$x = 0 \text{ and } b = 0$$

$$\forall a \in N$$

with $x \in \mathbf{Q}$

hence $a \in N$

Case 2) With $x^3 = b \in N$ and $a = 0$

Hence the terms of unipotent group have in both cases the cardinality $N = \aleph_0$.

Like in both cases the values of x form a subset hence each case form a subgroup.

Def. Ramification in algebraic number theory means a prime ideal factoring in an extension so as to give some repeated prime ideal factors. Namely, let O_K be the ring of integers of an algebraic number field K , and p a prime ideal of O_K . For a field extension L/K we can consider the ring of integers O_L (which is the integral closure of O_K in L , and the ideal $p \cdot O_L$ of O_L . This ideal may or may not be prime, but for finite $[L : K]$, it has a factorization into prime ideals:

$$pO_L = p_1^{e_1} p_k^{e_k}$$

where the p_i are distinct prime ideals of O_L . Then p is said to ramify in L if $e_i > 1$ for some i ; otherwise it is unramified. In other words, p ramifies in L if the ramification index e_i is greater than one for some p_i .

$$t_P = 3 \text{ (torus on three dimensions)}$$

$$u_P = 3 \text{ (degree equals to dimension)}$$

$\delta_P = k$ (prime factorization on k-elements)

$$f_P = 2u_P + t_P + \delta_P$$

$$= 3(n) + 3 + k$$

L-Hasse Weil can be used to define identity group element as:

If

$$\frac{2(n)+3+k}{p} \in N$$

$$\frac{2(n)+3+k}{p^2} \in N$$

Hence can be defined three different groups;

$$G_1 = \{g \mid g = 1 - a_p p^{-s} + p^{1-2s}\}$$

$$G_2 = \{g \mid g = 1 - a_p p^{-s}\}$$

$$G_3 = \{1\}$$

By group homomorphism condition about $h(e_G) = e_H$

$$L - HasseWeil(e_G) = e_H$$

with $e_G = x_i = z_j = 1$ or 0 considering addition and product; therefore the group properties can be defined since this characteristic; being trivial between elements $a, b \in \mathbf{Q}$

Def. A has good reduction at P if and only if $u_P = t_P = 0$ (which implies $f_P = \delta_P = 0$).

Proof.

$$t_P = 3 \text{ (torus on three dimensions)}$$

Hence A has no good reduction

For a curve E over \mathbf{Q} given by a minimal equation

$$y^2 + a_1xy + a_3y = x^3 + a_2x^2 + a_4x + a_6$$

with integral coefficients a_i , reducing the coefficients modulo p defines an elliptic curve over the finite field F_p .

Therefore the considered case is multiplicative reduction: a_p is ± 1 and the group definition can be identified as:

$$G_1 = \{g \mid g = 1 \pm p^{-s} + p^{1-2s}\}$$

$$G_2 = \{g \mid g = 1 \pm p^{-s}\}$$

$$G_3 = \{1\}$$

Def. Let be $f := L$ - Hasse Weil function

$$\ker f = \{g \in G : f(g) = e_H\}$$

Considering group G_3 definition hence

$$g = (1, 0) \text{ or } (0, 1)$$

and

$$e_H = 1$$

Cardinality of nilpotent group (how $x^n = 0$) is equal to n

The main parameter to define the dominion of (x, y, z) is r and R on torus.

this means that r and R its related with the value of x^n (and x, y and z)

with $x \in \mathbf{Q}$

$$x^n = 0 \text{ iff } x = 0$$

$$\forall n \in N$$

While L-HW functions has image $G_1 \cup G_2 \cup G_3$

$$G_1 = \{g \mid g = 1 \pm p^{-s} + p^{1-2s}\}$$

$$G_2 = \{g \mid g = 1 \pm p^{-s}\}$$

$$G_3 = \{1\}$$

Note that $L - HW(g) = 0$ iff $s = 0$ and $g = 1 - 1$

while with $s = 1$

L-HW has no zero

The condition

if $p|^{f_P}$ and p^{2f_P} ;

Establish that L-function is

$$(1 - a_p p^{-s}),$$

with $f_P = 3(n) + 3 + k$

and $x^n = 0$; with k defined since $p_1 \circ \dots \circ p_k$

If $n = N$ the cardinality of natural numbers; besides $s = 0$

the group with element point $x \in Q$; $x = \frac{p}{q}$

$$\frac{3N+3+k}{p} = \frac{3(N+1)+k}{p} \in N$$

$$\frac{3N+3+k}{p^2} = \frac{3(N+1)+k}{p^2} \notin N$$

Later the cases

If k is any prime (even or odd) and N prime (even or odd) the quotient is defined as...

$2a = \text{pair}$

$2a + 1 = \text{odd}$

$$\frac{3(2a+1)+(2a+1)}{p} = \frac{8a+4}{p}; \text{ (if } p = 2 \text{ hence the criteria is fulfilled)}$$

$\frac{3(2a)+(2a+1)}{p} = \frac{8a+1}{p}$; (if $8a + 1 = p^k$ hence $a = \frac{p^k-1}{8}$; hence the condition is fulfilled)

$$\frac{3(2a+1)+(2a)}{p} = \frac{8a+1}{p}; \text{ (and again like last condition)}$$

$$\frac{3(2a)+(2a)}{p} = \frac{6a}{p} \text{ (if } a = p \text{ hence the criteria is fulfilled)}$$

Def. In set theory, the Schröder–Bernstein theorem states that, if there exist injective functions $f : A \rightarrow B$ and $g : B \rightarrow A$ between the sets A and B , then there exists a bijective function $h : A \rightarrow B$.

In terms of the cardinality of the two sets, this classically implies that if $|A| \leq |B|$ and $|B| \leq |A|$, then $|A| = |B|$; that is, A and B are equipotent. This is a useful feature in the ordering of cardinal numbers.

$$\mathbf{Q}' = |\frac{1}{q}| = \aleph_0 ; \forall q \in N$$

hence

$$\mathbf{Q} = |\frac{p}{q}| = \aleph_0^2 ; \forall p, q \in N$$

Every real number has at least one infinite decimal expansion. For example,

$$1/2 = 0.50000\dots$$

$$1/3 = 0.33333\dots$$

$$\pi = 3.14159\dots$$

(This is true even in the case the expansion repeats, as in the first two examples.)

In any given case, the number of decimal places is countable since they can be put into a one-to-one correspondence with the set of natural numbers N . The infinite cardinal number is denoted by c (lowercase Fraktur "c") or $|\mathfrak{R}|$; $c = 2^{\aleph_0} > \aleph_0$

Lets use F the non-zero linear combination of third-degree monomials;

$$x^3, y^3, z^3, x^2y, x^2z, y^2x, y^2z, z^2x, z^2y, xyz$$

to define the group of the general cubic curve

$$y^2 = x^3 - ax - b$$

$$y = \pm\sqrt{x^3 - ax - b}$$

Like x^3 is one to one with $q \in N$; y is one to one with q; by counting twice taking into account the sign of square root hence the cardinality of $|E(\mathbf{Q})| = 2 \aleph_0$

$$L_P(E, s) = (1 - a_p p^{-s}), \text{ if } p|_{f_P} \text{ and } p \nmid f_P^2$$

The Taylor expansion of $L(E,s)$ at $s = 1$ has the form

$$(1 - a_p p^{-s}) + s(a_p)^{-s-1}(s - 1) + \dots$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\pm s! a_p p^{-s-n}}{n!} (s-1)^n$$

being different from $L(E, s) = a_p (s-1)^r + \text{Higher Order Terms}$

with $a_p \neq 0$ and $r = \text{rank}(E(\mathbf{Q}))$

In particular this conjecture asserts that $L(E, 1) = 0$ iff $E(\mathbf{Q})$ is infinite being false like was proved (true for $s = 0$).

4 References

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